

Aceh International Pharmacy Conference

"Herbal Medicine Management : From Laboratory to Market"

Celebrating the Silver Anniversary of Mathematics and Natural Sciences

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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**Optimization Condition Of Method Development Simultaneous
Determination Sweeteners, Preservatives And Dyes In Essences Syrup
Using High Performance
Liquid Chromatography**

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Abstract

Syrup is a popular beverage product and consumed by people. Syrup should not contain artificial sweeteners, preservatives and dyes except. Sweeteners, preservatives and dyes can be hazardous to health if they are over consumed. The purpose of this research was to obtained a method to determination simultaneous of tartrazine, sunset yellow, saccharin, cyclamate, benzoic and sorbic in essence syrup using high performance liquid chromatography. The study used high-performance liquid chromatography reverse phase two wavelengths with instruments UFLC 1290 DAD (Agilent), C18 column 100 mm x 4.6 mm (Agilent), Probe UV 1800 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu), standard material tartrazine, sunset yellow, sodium saccharin, sodium cyclamate, sodium benzoate and potassium sorbate. Optimization parameters include wavelength, void volume, mobile phase composition, flow rate and oven temperature. The method obtained is then used for the determination of tartrazine, sunset yellow, saccharin, cyclamate, benzoic and sorbic in syrup essences samples. The results showed that the optimum conditions for the test is the wavelength of 200 nm for the detection of cyclamate, a wavelength of 220 nm for the detection of tartrazine, saccharin, sunset yellow, benzoate and sorbate, 30% void volume, mobile phase pH 4.5 phosphate buffer : methanol (75 : 25, v / v), flow rate of 0.8 ml/min, oven temperature of 30°C.

Keywords : Tartrazine, saccharin, cyclamate, Sunset Yellow, Benzoate, Sorbic, High Performance Liquid Chromatography, Optimization, Syrup Essences.